

In the Court(s) We Trust?

On the need for hierarchy and differentiation in the preliminary ruling procedure

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The article advocates limitation of lower courts' power to send preliminary references. It shows that many arguments against such an approach are not sufficiently thought out and are used rather mechanically. The proposal sees national judicial hierarchy as an important element of the Union judicial process, which can make the preliminary ruling procedure rational and effective, while keeping its original purpose. At the same time it suggests some measures that strike the balance between judicial protection of individuals and effectiveness. The key idea behind the proposal is the need for more trust in national courts, if they are to be truly considered as Union courts.

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I. Introduction

There is certainly no shortage of articles devoted to the judicial system of the European Union and proposals for its reform, particularly with respect to the preliminary ruling procedure. Although the backlog of cases pending before the Court of Justice has been reduced in the last two years, the present shape of the preliminary ruling procedure cannot be considered satisfactory. This is particularly so with regard to the time it requires. Most of the proposals, made either by academics or various institutions, have rejected one option, which would reduce the Court of Justice's caseload significantly: limiting the procedure to national courts of last instance only. Arguments put forward against this option are many and have considerable weight. Very often, however, they are based on an implicit distrust of national courts and their competence or even willingness to make EU law effective in their respective legal orders.

Contrary to these voices, this article suggests the following:

- 1 Limiting preliminary ruling procedure to courts of last instance as a rule;
- 2 As a *necessary* exception to 1, when a lower court considers that one or more arguments for invalidity, put forward by the parties or as the case may be raised by it of its own motion, are well founded, it must stay proceedings and make a reference to the Court for a preliminary ruling on the act's validity;

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- 3 As a *possible* exception to 1, the Council can decide which EU law measures may be subject to preliminary references from lower courts.

The article therefore opposes a recent Commission’s Communication,¹ which illustrates well the prevailing attitude to the preliminary ruling procedure. The Communication proposes to make the ordinary Article 234 EC preliminary reference procedure fully applicable to the provisions of Title IV of the EC Treaty. Title IV encompasses provisions dealing with visas, and asylum and immigration policies, together with judicial cooperation in civil matters. Today, the jurisdiction of the Court of Justice in this field is limited and only courts of last instance may refer preliminary questions.² The Communication resulted in a proposal for a Council decision, which should make Article 234 EC fully applicable in Title IV. The main argument on which the Commission bases its proposal is a need for uniformity of EC law, effective judicial protection of individuals’ rights, and trust in the proper functioning of the Court of Justice, which according to the Commission is now prepared to cope with its inevitably increased caseload.

The Commission’s proposal is based on a prevailing, but certainly not the only possible conception of the Union judicial system; a conception, which sees the Court of Justice as the superior and exclusive judicial institution for making the EU legal system functional. This understanding distrusts national courts, when it turns the preliminary ruling procedure from a tool for achieving unity and coherence of EU law to a mechanism for the judicial protection of individuals. At the same time, the goal of uniformity is pushed to absurdity and serves as a justification of the Court of Justice’s excessive intervention into the national judicial process. As will be shown, due to its structural characteristics the preliminary ruling procedure can never serve these aims properly, although the Court of Justice itself contributes to this expectation, largely supported by the legal doctrine.³

This article offers an alternative conception of the EU judicial system: a conception which sees national courts as *true* parts of the EU judicial system. Too often national judges are only reminded of their Union mission when obligations in the name of effective application of EU law are imposed upon them. But this mission must also entail more trust in them, as well as a consideration of problems which these obligations may cause to national judicial processes. National and Union judicial processes are connected vessels and problems at one level inevitably cause problems at another.

This article sees hierarchy as an important element of any judicial process, which makes the process rational and effective. The current preliminary ruling procedure undermines national judicial hierarchies when it allows any court to enter into a dialogue with the Court of Justice. While this openness certainly played an important role in the formative years of the EU legal order, maintaining it today seems less justified. The alternative conception of the preliminary

¹ “Adaptation of the provisions of Title IV of the Treaty establishing the European Community relating to the jurisdiction of the Court of Justice with a view to ensuring more effective judicial protection”, COM(2006) 346 final, hereafter “the Communication.” The Court of Justice issued two discussion papers related to the Communication, both available at <<http://www.curia.europa.eu/en/instit/txtdocfr/index.htm>>, hereafter “the Discussion Paper” and “the Discussion Paper Supplement”.

² Article 68 EC.

³ For a thoughtful critique of the Court of Justice’s distrust of national courts’ independent application of EU law see Gareth Davies, “Abstractness and concreteness in the preliminary ruling procedure: implications for the division of powers and effective market regulation”, in: Shuibhne, N.N. (ed), *Regulating the Internal Market* (Edward Elgar, 2006). Davies calls this “infantilising and marginalising the role of national courts in interpreting Community law” (p. 212).

ruling procedure would thus suggest limiting the possibility to refer preliminary rulings to last instance courts only, as is now the case in Title IV matters. Hence “the need for hierarchy”.

In addition, the preliminary ruling procedure covers too divergent types of judicial procedures concerning various fields of substantive law. It does not distinguish whether it arises in a criminal procedure, where the rights of individuals must be particularly carefully treated, a dispute between two undertakings, which concern a considerable amount of money, or a matter of constitutional importance. This calls for a “differentiation”, which in certain cases makes desirable the allowing of references from lower courts as well and in some cases inserting a truly expedited procedure, not a procedure which takes almost the same time as an ordinary one.⁴ The article asks whether we trust courts and is intentionally formulated ambiguously. It also asks whether we should trust the Court of Justice’s ability to fulfil the role ascribed to it by the EU founding treaties. At the same time, the article examines whether we sufficiently trust national courts as European courts.

The article will proceed as follows: Firstly it will take issue with arguments presented against limitation of the preliminary ruling procedure to last instance courts only (part II). It will be seen that these arguments often contain much deeper normative claims, which are not discernible on the surface. Identifying them will help clarify the debate about the Union judiciary, and focus it on the real issues instead of slogans. After this, the Court of Justice’s improved efficiency will be critically assessed (part III). Finally, after providing an account of the Court of Justice’s role and showing why hierarchy is important in securing efficiency of the judicial system, a more detailed proposal on how the preliminary reference should look will be provided (part IV).

II. Arguments against limitation of the preliminary ruling procedure to last instance courts

This part will discuss the main arguments put forward against limitation of the preliminary ruling procedure to the last instance courts only. As will be seen, too often are some concepts used in the debate without their being critically examined. The following hopes to clarify these concepts in order to steer the debate to the real issues posed by the limitation of the Court of Justice’s jurisdiction in the preliminary ruling procedure.

a) Uniformity and authority of EU law

Uniformity is like a magic formula, preventing many proposals on decentralization of the preliminary ruling procedure. Consider the following words used by the Court of Justice:

Any weakening, even if only potential, of the uniform application and interpretation of Community law throughout the Union would be liable to give rise to distortions of competition and discrimination between economic operators, thus jeopardizing equality of opportunity as between those operators and consequently the proper functioning of the internal market. One of the Court's essential tasks is to ensure just such a uniform interpretation, and it discharges that duty by answering the questions

⁴ See part III. a) *infra*.

put to it by the national courts and tribunals. The possibility of referring a question to the Court of Justice must therefore remain open to all those courts and tribunals.⁵

The first problem arising here is what the Court of Justice means by uniformity. Is it an *absolute* “sameness”, suggested by the warning that even potential weakening of uniformity could have disastrous consequences for the internal market? If so, it would make EU law indeed unique, since no legal system can achieve such a degree of uniformity as the Court of Justice suggests. Practices of the highest national courts show that this cannot be the case. As Chalmers puts it:

Unity of interpretation does not mean that the highest court should provide rulings on every provision. Within most national legal systems, higher national courts, with far more wide-ranging jurisdictions, guarantee the unity and ordered development of their legal systems through setting out a number of steering judgments each year, which define the hallmarks of that legal order and guide other actors in how to apply the law.⁶

One important note must be made here. There are some supreme courts,⁷ whose caseload is not controlled by any means. The most extreme example is the Italian Supreme Court, *Corte di Cassazione*, which must decide every case arising before it as a matter of constitutional right, guaranteed to all citizens.⁸ Consequently, this court decides about 12 000 civil cases and 35 000 criminal cases a year. For such a task it is composed of 400 judges. However, it would be erroneous to think that the *Corte di Cassazione*’s massive intervention in the judicial system’s operation achieves greater uniformity of law. To the contrary: “[an] essay concerning conflicts [judgments] in civil matters, which consider[ed] only five years and judgments published by 12 legal journals, show[ed] that the court ha[d] fallen into contradiction no less than 864 times.”⁹ More “precedents” simply does not mean more uniformity.

The example of the U.S. Supreme Court also shows that striving for uniformity through case law does not mean that the Supreme Court decides every case brought forth. The Supreme Court sometimes leaves the lower or State (!) courts to work out a new rule and intervenes only after some decisions have significantly differed among these courts. As (now former) Justice O’Connor says:

While uniformity is a necessary and desirable goal, its immediate achievement is not always possible. Nor is immediate action necessarily desirable. Part of the beauty of our federalism is the diversity of viewpoint it brings to bear on legal problems. State court judges may have a different approach to a problem than might a federal judge; the lessons that can be learned from being a judge in one part of our country will not

⁵ Report of the Court of Justice on certain aspects of the application of the Treaty on European Union, 1995, point 11.

⁶ Damian Chalmers, “The Dynamics of Judicial Authority and the Constitutional Treaty” in: Weiler, J.H.H., Eysgruber, C.L. (eds), *Alneuland: The EU Constitution in a Contextual Perspective*, Jean Monnet Working Paper 5/04, <<http://www.jeanmonnetprogram.org/papers/04/040501-18.html>> at p. 22.

⁷ E.g. Italy, Spain or Poland. However, civilian systems also have adopted some measures to limit access to its supreme courts. See Michele Taruffo, “Institutional Factors Influencing Precedents” in: MacCormick, N. and Summers R.S. (eds), *Interpreting Precedents: A Comparative Study* (Aldershot, 1997) at pp. 445-446.

⁸ See Michele Taruffo and Massimo La Torre, “Precedent in Italy” in: MacCormick, N. and Summers R.S. (eds), *Interpreting Precedents: A Comparative Study* (Aldershot, 1997) at p. 144.

⁹ *Ibid* at p. 165.

be immediately obvious to those who have always lived, practiced, and judged in another part. [...] When those courts encounter an unresolved question of federal law, their differing perspectives may lead them to different conclusions. The resulting divergence provides a valuable moment in the law -- a moment of dialogue among different jurists in which they may share their views on a common issue. There can be no doubt that the dialogue is a profitable one or that the Court on which I sit listens to the voices in the debate.¹⁰

Problems stem from an unclear meaning of uniformity in general. Whereas uniformity is used as a part of law's rhetoric, the examples above show that virtually no legal system may ever achieve it. Recently, the very dogma of uniformity in Community law application has started to be questioned, most prominently by Dougan, who advocates a differentiated approach to the system of national remedies, which would reflect regulatory differentiation that is real in certain sectors of Community policy.¹¹ What may be added to Dougan's arguments is that no legal system, even unitary, achieves or even aims at uniformity in such absolute terms as Community law claims (but necessarily fails to provide) for itself.¹² All mechanisms of case filtration existing in various jurisdictions confirm this regardless of the criteria these mechanisms adopt – it means that some questions are not important enough to be decided by the supreme interpretative authority of the system. Why should the Community legal system be different?

The argument of uniformity in fact contains far more than the need for coherent legal order. Dyberg's words explain it a little: "Uniform application is rather a sort of existential problem to which the Community legal order has to relate."¹³ To see the importance of this "existential problem," we must understand what uniformity may actually mean for a legal system: "[I]n the national legal systems, uniform application is mostly taken for granted."¹⁴ As we know, it is not necessarily always true, but the core of this assertion lies in the fact that there is a *presumption of uniformity* in the national law. The fact that we do not even think what uniformity really means only confirms how deeply we connect it with a functional legal order in which we are used to live. On the other hand, EU law must fight for these *presumptions* being attached to it in the national legal orders. Only then may it claim its authoritative status of the law of the land.

The control over national courts' practices regarding EU law is another element underlying the Court of Justice's desire for uniformity. The Court of Justice is not greatly troubled about EU law being applied with some discrepancies before various national courts. After all, the Court of Justice itself contributes to non-uniform application of EU law in certain areas. Chalmers gives an example of the state regulation of gambling and its relationship to the internal market freedoms, where the Court has been giving inconsistent answers in almost every judgment it delivered,¹⁵ but other examples could certainly be found as well. In some cases the Court of Justice even denied creating a uniform rule, although this was badly needed

¹⁰ Sandra Day O'Connor, "Proceedings of the Middle Atlantic State-Federal Judicial Relationships Conference", (1994) 162 Fed.Rules Dec. 173 at pp. 181-82.

¹¹ See Michael Dougan, *National Remedies before the Court of Justice. Issues of Harmonisation and Differentiation* (Hart Publishing, 2004), particularly at pp. 113-226.

¹² See Chalmers, op. cit. n. 6 at pp. 22-23.

¹³ Peter Dyberg, "What Should the Court of Justice Be Doing?", (2001) 26 E.L.Rev. 291 at 295.

¹⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵ Chalmers, op. cit. n. 6 at p. 23.

and asked for.¹⁶ Thus uniformity cannot be the main concern. The Court rather fears that EU law would not be applied at all. The strong (and unrealistic) strive for uniformity serves as a justification for the Court of Justice’s involvement in cases of minor importance for EU legal order as a whole, where an ordinary supreme court in a mature system of law would never intervene. This intervention does not aim at uniformity, but supremacy of Union law.¹⁷

For a better understanding of this aspect of the Court of Justice’s construction of the notion of uniformity, which in fact serves as a justification for its broad involvement in national courts’ decision-making activity, the U.S. concept of “federal question jurisdiction” may provide some insights. The federal jurisdiction clause in the U.S. Constitution determines what kinds of cases may be heard before federal instead of state courts.¹⁸ Justification for federal jurisdiction is based on three considerations: more experience of federal judges to deal with federal law, hope of uniformity in application of federal law, and finally, more solicitude for its proper application than could be expected from state courts judges.¹⁹ So it is not only the need for correct application of federal law (hence “experience”), nor uniformity which justifies jurisdiction of federal courts in certain cases. One limb of the justification for federal jurisdiction lies in the protection of federal law from unfaithful treatment by state courts. A similar point can be made in a historical perspective: “Historically, Congress’ regulation of the Supreme Court’s jurisdiction in relation to the state courts demonstrates a congressional perception that the Supreme Court’s main role is to ensure the supremacy rather than the uniformity of federal law.”²⁰ The Court of Justice, by its broadly construed construction of uniformity, does the same.

However, this is rooted in the Court of Justice’s distrust in national higher courts. Of course, there are examples where some supreme courts failed to refer important questions to the Court of Justice or even ignored its rulings. The most famous would probably be the French *Conseil d’Etat*, which did not recognize the direct effect of directives for a considerable period of time.²¹ This may be true, but the remedy for this situation was certainly not the possibility of the lower courts sending preliminary references to the Court of Justice. It was the *Conseil d’Etat* itself which eventually changed its attitude and confirmed that directives may have a direct effect in its celebrated *Nicolo* decision.²² Even if lower courts could send references to the Court of Justice, asking whether directives were or were not directly effective, it was ultimately the *Conseil d’Etat* which determined whether this would be true in France (or before French administrative courts at least, as the *Cour de Cassation* took a different

¹⁶ Consider e.g. a distinction between discriminatory and non-discriminatory obstacles to the free movement, important for their possible justification (whether it is possible on express grounds enlisted in the Treaties only or on the case-law based justifications as well). Advocate General F. Jacobs in his opinion in Case C-136/00 Danner [2002] ECR I-8147 expressly pointed out the two lines of cases, each of them leading to different results, and invited the Court to clarify the correct application. The Court, however, did not respond to his call.

¹⁷ This point is nicely proven in a recent contribution of Koen Lenaerts and Tim Corthaut, “Of Birds and Hedges: The Role of Primacy in Invoking Norms of EU Law”, (2006) 31 E.L.Rev. 287 at pp. 289-291, where they argue for the supremacy of the second and third pillar EU law from uniformity.

¹⁸ U.S.Const. art. III, § 2, cl. 1.

¹⁹ See *Grable & Sons Metal Products Inc. v. Darue Engineering & Manufacturing Co.*, 125 U.S. 2363 (2005) at p. 2368.

²⁰ J. Clifford Wallace, “The Nature and Extent of Intercircuit Conflicts: A Solution Needed for a Mountain or a Molehill?” (1983) 71 Calif.L.Rev. 913 at p. 917.

²¹ Judgment of 22.12. 1978, *Minister of the Interior v. Daniel Cohn-Bendit*, [1980] 1 C.M.L.R. 543.

²² Judgment of 20.10. 1989, *Raoul Georges Nicolo and Another*, [1990] 1 C.M.L.R. 173.

approach).²³ Similarly, in the case of the German *Bundesfinanzhof*, it was the Federal Constitutional Court (*Bundesverfassungsgericht*) which made this court accept the same doctrine,²⁴ regardless of the Court of Justice's unequivocal response to a reference coming from a lower court,²⁵ since the *Bundesfinanzhof* quashed its decisions.²⁶ The highest courts hold a veto power over the Court of Justice's rulings within their legal orders²⁷ and lower courts have only limited means to change it.

Another response, which could satisfy those who share this sceptical approach to national supreme courts, is the fact that the Court of Justice now has a greater control over supreme courts than ever before.²⁸ A national judge is no more immune from causing liability of the state – either in relation to individuals or the Community in infringement proceedings. This stems from the recent case law of the court in *Köbler*²⁹ and *Commission v. Italy*.³⁰ Although viability of the principles set in these judgments may be seriously questioned, their power lies outside actual cases where they could be successfully invoked – it lies in their dissuasive effects. Parties may use them to warn national judges not to disregard EU law³¹ and it seems that Court of Justice judges themselves never let slip an opportunity to remind their national counterparts of these judgments, of course, in an atmosphere of sincere cooperation and mutual understanding.³² Equally, although the Commission will scarcely (if ever) pursue a case of infringement based on judicial breaches ultimately to the Court of Justice, it may use *Commission v. Italy* as a precedent to dissuade the Member States. Actually, Sweden has recently had to change its rules of civil procedure and, whenever a court dismisses an appeal without referring to the Court of Justice although parties have sought this, it must give reasons.³³

Having hopefully satisfied sceptics, this article is nevertheless based on a different approach: on the real trust in national courts. The instances of national highest courts' open rebellions against the Court of Justice have been few, although they (regrettably) serve as perfect evidence for anyone wishing to point them out as proofs of the danger of our trusting in these courts. It is submitted, however, that in most instances when these courts did not send references to the Court of Justice, they acted thus for good reasons. As Chalmers suggests:

²³ See Monica Claes, *The National Courts' Mandate in the European Constitution* (Hart Publishing, 2006) at pp. 224-231.

²⁴ Judgment of 8.4. 1987 *Kloppenburger* [1988] 3 C.M.L.R. 1.

²⁵ Case 70/83 *Kloppenburger* [1984] ECR 1075.

²⁶ Judgment of 16.6. 1981 [1982] 1 C.M.L.R. 527. See on the story Claes, op. cit. n. 23 at pp. 429-431.

²⁷ Damian Chalmers, "Judicial Preferences and the Community Legal Order", (1997) 60 M.L.R. 164 at p. 180.

²⁸ See generally Jan Komárek, "Federal Elements in the Community Judicial System: Building Coherence in the Community Legal Order", (2005) 42 C.M.L.Rev. 9.

²⁹ Case C-224/01 *Köbler* [2003] ECR I-10239.

³⁰ Case C-129/00 *Commission v Italy* [2003] ECR I-14637.

³¹ See e.g. Berend Jan Drijber (attorney at the Dutch Bar), Council of Bars and Law Societies of Europe (CCBE), "Papers from the Colloquium on the Judicial Architecture of the European Union 15 November 2004", available at <http://www.ccbe.org/doc/colloquium_nov_2004/documents.htm> at p. 35.

³² See e.g. contribution of Judge Jann to the general meeting of the European Network of Councils for the Judiciary, Barcelona, 2.-3.6. 2005 "The responsibility of judges in Europe", conference proceedings available at <www.csm.it/pages/ENCJ/ENCJ%20conference%20report%20Barcelona.pdf> or contribution of the Court of Justice President Skouris at the conference "The Position of Constitutional Courts Following Integration into the European Union", Bled, 30.9.-2.10. 2004 available at <<http://www.us-rs.si/en>>.

³³ See Ulf Bernitz, "The Duty of Supreme Courts to Refer Cases to the ECJ: The Commission's Action Against Sweden" in: Wahl, N. and Cramér, P. (eds), *Swedish Studies in European Law - Volume 1, 2006* (Hart Publishing, 2006).

Even a brief perusal of the cases suggests this was not some systematic rejection of the Court of Justice’s authority. The overwhelming majority of cases involved significant commercial interests where speedy resolution and legal certainty were considered to be particularly important. If a matter was not general and important, national courts of last resort do not refer.³⁴

Reports from the Conference of the national Supreme Administrative Courts seem to confirm this.³⁵ These courts know that their main objective is to solve the disputes brought to them by the parties rather than create a new legal order in sincere cooperation with the Court of Justice, which means that some questions remain without their reference.

One may object that such confidence is no longer possible in times where in 2004 ten Member States acceded to the Union. It is accurate to say that these Member States’ judiciaries still meet serious problems.³⁶ However (although it involves some measure of an informed guess rather than empirically based evidence), these courts do not contest the authority of EU law or the Court of Justice. One should not be misled by some constitutional courts’ rhetoric used in the judgments in which they define the relationship of their constitutions to EU law. The rhetoric is intended for internal discourse. What these courts *actually* show is their respect for obligations arising from EU law.³⁷

In sum, whether or not we take an optimistic approach towards the highest national courts, there are no longer any good reasons for allowing the lower courts to circumvent their authority, either because the EU has the mechanisms for making disobedient courts toe the line or because there is no reason to believe that these courts’ intention be to compromise the Court of Justice’s authority in a systematic manner.

b) Judicial protection of individuals and economy of the judicial process

Effective judicial protection of individuals together with procedural economy is a second powerful argument against reserving preliminary reference procedure to last instance courts. The time and effort of private litigants is said to justify the direct link of even the lowest courts to the Court of Justice. However, the very same argument may be used the other way round: preliminary ruling procedure considerably delays the final judgment and causes additional costs. So where to strike the balance?

One thing should be made clear: while the preliminary ruling procedure may serve individual justice in a *wider* perspective, by guiding national courts in their application of EU law, and thus making the whole system deciding more correctly and just, it can never systematically provide justice in every single case. Chalmers suggests that the problem of the Court of Justice’s caseload would be particularly acute in the Area of Freedom, Security and Justice, as

³⁴ Chalmers, *op. cit.* n. 6 at p. 34.

³⁵ This was discussed by the Association of the Councils of State and Supreme Administrative Jurisdictions of the European Union at its 19th Colloquium. See the General Report from the Colloquium, <http://193.191.217.21/colloquia/2004/gen_report_en.pdf> at pp. 71-73.

³⁶ See e.g. Zdeněk Kühn, “Worlds Apart. Western and Central European Judicial Culture at the Onset of the European Enlargement,” (2004) 52 *Am.J.Comp.L.* 531.

³⁷ See Wojciech Sadurski, “‘Solange, chapter 3’: Constitutional Courts in Central Europe – Democracy – European Union”, EUI Working Paper Law 2006/40, available at <<http://hdl.handle.net/1814/6420>>. For an excellent overview of the ordinary courts’ practice in the Member States, which acceded in 2004, see Michal Bobek, “A New or Non-Existent Legal Order? Some (Early) Experience in the Application of EU Law in Central Europe”, (2006) 3 *Croatian Yearbook of European Law and Policy* 265.

it “will no longer cover narrow fields of law, which rarely generate matters of headline-generating sensitivity. It will now dominate the heartlands of domestic judicial activity and intrude regularly into areas of acute national sensitivity.”³⁸ This would mean even more references sent to the Court of Justice. To propose widening the scope of Article 234 EC to Title IV of the EC Treaty, as the current Commission’s proposal does, is to ignore this. To the contrary, limitation of the Court of Justice’s jurisdiction should be seriously considered.

A potentially powerful argument against limiting lower courts’ competence to ask the Court of Justice lies in the possible threat to the economy of national procedure. The argument goes that a party would have to climb the judicial hierarchy to the point where there was no appeal for its being allowed to raise its EU law arguments before a court with the ultimate authority to hear them and make a decision. However, this presumes that every question of EU must be dealt with by the Court of Justice, and disregards the fact of the same painful exercise the parties must undertake if they wish to get the national supreme court to clarify some important point of purely national law. Why should the litigants, playing the “EU law card”, be treated differently?

It must be stressed that such an exercise in the appellate procedure may significantly reduce the number of instances where the top of the system is eventually reached. And this is exactly the point. Only if the litigants are sure of their claim and the lower courts have not persuaded them of the correctness of their judgment, have they sufficient incentives to undertake the whole appellate exercise. The effect of this is fewer cases of greater importance arising before the supreme court. It is painful, no doubt, but it is a necessary price for the judicial system’s effective functioning. The only possible exceptions to the hierarchical organization of the judicial procedure are perhaps referrals to constitutional courts existing in some legal systems. But these concern the most fundamental questions of constitutionality and not e.g. the tariff classification of pyjamas.³⁹ The attempt to attach fundamental status to every provision of EU law is contradicting the premise that EU law has become part of national law. If it has, then EU law can no longer be treated as “supranational” law having some special force in each instance, rather must the weight of its rules reflect their actual nature.

Preliminary ruling procedure must be seen as a deviation from normal organization of the judicial process, not as its natural component. This is because it allows obviating the existing hierarchy amongst the courts, which plays an important role in the rationalization of the judicial process,⁴⁰ and delays final resolution of the dispute, thus potentially bringing an element of injustice. Again, it is a question of how we want to see the EU judicial system: whether it really comprises national courts *as* European courts, or whether we use this label only for highlighting their obligations resulting from EU law. If we see it in the former sense, than we must accept that it means to see the EU judiciary as a judicial system without qualifications. Nice labels may only hide some (of course hard) choices we must inevitably make when we perceive national courts as “Community courts of general jurisdiction”⁴¹ – thus fully competent to decide questions concerning interpretation of EU law. Insisting on all courts’ possibility to refer to the Court of Justice questions their competence to give effective protection to individuals without the Court of Justice’s assistance. At the same time, it implies that the Court should be involved in an everyday dispute settlement whenever a question of

³⁸ Chalmers, *op. cit.* n. 6 at 16.

³⁹ The “Pyjama Case” (Case C-338/95 Wiener [1997] ECR I-6495) is the famous one, where Advocate General Jacobs proposed that the Court of Justice change its criteria for obligatory references.

⁴⁰ On the role of hierarchies in national judicial systems see part IV b) *infra*.

⁴¹ Case T-51/89 Tetra Pak [1990] ECR II-309, para. 42, cited in Claes, *op. cit.* n. 23 at p. 3.

Community law arises, regardless of its importance for the EU legal system as a whole. The result is an unreasonable distribution of the Court of Justice’s judicial capacity throughout the Union judicial system.

Moreover, one may doubt whether the preliminary ruling procedure can truly be considered to serve individual justice, if the Court of Justice itself holds that “Article 234 EC establishes direct cooperation between the Court and the courts and tribunals of the Member States by way of a non-contentious procedure excluding any initiative of the parties, who are merely invited to be heard in the course of that procedure”.⁴² So, individual rights are said to be at stake before the Court of Justice, but those to whom these rights pertain are “merely invited to be heard”, not to defend their case, with all the consequences which would follow from this (such as the right to defence, the right to be heard or, more broadly, the right to a fair trial). Such a dismissive attitude to the parties is particularly striking if we realize that, in references concerning alleged invalidity of a Community measure, it is solely the Court of Justice which may decide. So far the European Court of Human Rights has taken a very benevolent attitude, e.g. when it did not take into account the time necessary for the preliminary procedure on assessing whether the final judgment of a Greek court which referred to the Court of Justice was excessively delayed.⁴³ It is an open question whether this did not change after the ECHR confirmed the importance of the preliminary ruling procedure in the system of judicial protection of the EU in *Bosphorus v. Ireland*.⁴⁴ The Human Rights Court, however, clearly misrepresented the standing of individuals in the preliminary ruling procedure, when it said that “[t]he parties to the domestic proceedings have the right to put their case to the Court of Justice during the Art.[234] process. It is further recalled that national courts operate in legal systems into which the Convention has been incorporated, albeit to differing degrees.” No such right exists, at least as a matter of Community law, and the Court of Justice has confirmed this on several occasions.

There should, however, be room for at least one exception allowing lower courts’ preliminary references. Individuals who believe that their rights have been violated by a Community measure adopted under Title IV must now, according to *Foto-Frost*,⁴⁵ go through the national judicial hierarchy to the court of last instance to be able to plead invalidity before a court solely competent to review Community measures: the Court of Justice. Many rightly criticize this⁴⁶ and there are no compelling reasons to prevent lower courts from questioning validity of Community law in cooperation with the Court of Justice.

Allowing the lower courts to do so does not contradict the approach suggested here, an approach which promotes rational distribution of the Court of Justice’s judicial capacity by limiting its jurisdiction to cases of importance for the legal system. Questions of validity are without a doubt important. Moreover, *Foto-Frost* does not imply that the national court must refer every single case, which raises doubts about the validity of a Community measure. If the national court is not convinced by arguments claiming invalidity, it may decide without the Court of Justice’s assistance.⁴⁷ The exclusion of lower courts from referring questions concerning validity of Community measures goes in the opposite direction to the Court of Justice’s construction of the Community system of remedies reinforced in *Unión de Pequeños*

⁴² Case C-496/04 *Slob*, not yet reported, para. 34.

⁴³ Case *Pafitis v. Greece* [1999] 27 E.H.R.R. 566, para. 95.

⁴⁴ Case *Bosphorus v. Ireland* [2006] 42 E.H.R.R. 1, para. 164.

⁴⁵ Case 314/85 *Foto-Frost* [1987] ECR 4199.

⁴⁶ See *Claes*, op. cit. n. 23 at pp. 578-583 with further references and Communication, p. 5.

⁴⁷ See e.g. recently Case C-344/04 *International Air Transport Association*, not yet reported, paras. 27-32.

Agricultores v. Council;⁴⁸ this restricts individuals' direct access to the Court of Justice and refers them to national courts, which are then obliged to ask the Court for a preliminary ruling. The system of individuals' effective judicial protection becomes even more illusory if there is no possibility for national courts to refer the question of validity to the Court of Justice. These courts may only invite the parties to appeal to a higher court (competent to turn to the Court of Justice) in order to obtain a judgment, which the deciding lower court itself believes to be right or just.

In addition to this exception, it may be considered that in some cases the exclusion of lower courts from the preliminary ruling procedure compromises economy of the judicial process as a whole. The Brussels regulation⁴⁹ is a perfect example since it is a basic principle to determine jurisdiction of a court at the earliest stage of the procedure possible so that judicial resources are not wasted in producing a decision, which would eventually be annulled because an incompetent court had delivered it.⁵⁰

Judicial protection of individuals and procedural economy therefore may justify allowing in certain instances references from lower courts. This should however be the exception and not the rule, as it is today.

c) Broader considerations concerning the role of lower courts in the development of EU law

The last set of arguments concerns the overall role of lower courts in the development of EU law. It is asserted that almost three fourths of all references come from these courts and that without these references the Court of Justice would have no possibility of creating the doctrines now widely accepted as most fundamental for the Community legal order. It has been claimed that it is a kind of tradition to allow all courts to enter into a dialogue with the Court of Justice. From the point of view of national legal orders, it has been argued that "the ability of any national court or tribunal to refer has been of importance in emphasizing the penetration of EC law to all points of the national legal system."⁵¹ These are strong arguments which touch the more fundamental questions concerning the role of lower courts in the European legal integration project – similarly as with the "hidden" core of the argument from uniformity, discussed above. But still, the arguments are not as incontestable as they may seem.

The argument regarding the number of references is easy to rebut – the very aim of our proposal is to make the Court of Justice's caseload more reasonable. Similarly, lower courts do not have to feel isolated from EU law by its being impossible for them to consult the Court of Justice. Today, it is almost impossible to find a field of national law untouched by EU law. Not only are judges much better educated, so are the parties who invoke EU law before these lower courts – which are often not competent enough and would rather send a reference to Luxembourg, pressed by the parties' advocates, than try to find for themselves the correct response to the problem posed by EU law. This need to find an answer without the possibility of easily avoiding the problem by referring it to the Court of Justice would be "a most valuable training ground, and [would] be a development in conformity with the principle of

⁴⁸ Case C-50/00 P *Unión de Pequeños Agricultores v. Council* [2002] ECR I-6677.

⁴⁹ Council Regulation (EC) No 44/2001 of 22 December 2000 on jurisdiction and the recognition and enforcement of judgments in civil and commercial matters, OJ 2001, L 12, p. 1.

⁵⁰ This principle can be derived by analogy from Case 34/82 *Peters* [1983] ECR 987, para. 17.

⁵¹ Paul Craig, "The Jurisdiction of the Community Courts Reconsidered" in: De Búrca G., Weiler J.H.H. (eds.) *The European Court of Justice* (Oxford University Press, 2001) at p. 196.

subsidiarity”⁵² and not a step isolating lower courts from all EU law. It would only highlight their responsibility as Community courts of general jurisdiction, by signalling that finding solutions based on EU law is not only work for the Luxembourg oracle, but also for them.

Whether the development of EU law would be threatened by limiting preliminary references to the highest courts is only questionable – first, because it cannot be excluded that an “important” preliminary reference from a lower court would reach the Court of Justice as a reference from a higher court too. Second, all depends on how we define “important” questions. It has been proposed elsewhere that preliminary references are “another infant disease” of the Community legal order.⁵³ It may well be the time to reflect on whether we need the Court of Justice to give a ruling on the interpretation of every provision of EU law that we can think of or whether its role should be more that of a genuine Supreme and Constitutional Court of the Union, in a more mature legal system. The latter view is well characterised by Advocate General Jacobs:

[T]he Court’s primary task in preliminary rulings is not to decide specific cases on the basis of narrowly distinguished facts, or to solve a problem for the national court in the particular case, but to state clearly and coherently for the benefit of everyone in the Community what the correct understanding of the law is, and to give rulings of general significance. It is only that broader function which justifies the system of preliminary rulings and explains the unique procedure whereby Member States and the Commission are systematically invited to submit observations and indeed why the judgment of the Court and the Opinion of the Advocate General in every case are published in no fewer than 11 languages.⁵⁴

This article reflects this appeal. Unfortunately, the Court of Justice seems to be heading in the opposite direction.

III. Efficiency of the Court of Justice

a) “Trust in the proper functioning of the Court of Justice” – through the looking glass

In its Communication, the Commission considers that “the Court, the efficiency of the means of internal organization which it now enjoys and the new possibilities created by the Nice Treaty must be trusted.”⁵⁵ The President of the Court of Justice is similarly optimistic about the increasing effectiveness of the Court of Justice.⁵⁶ Should we therefore still care about the caseload in the preliminary ruling procedure?

The Communication highlights the fact that “the Court has managed to significantly reduce the average duration of preliminary ruling proceedings.”⁵⁷ However, the Commission fails to add that, since 1 May 2004, the Court has had 10 more judges while the number of cases arising from the new Member States (taking into account all kinds of cases, not only

⁵² Hjalte Rasmussen, “Remedying the Crumbling EC Judicial System”, (2000) 37 C.M.L.Rev. 1071 at p. 1107.

⁵³ Philip Allot, “Preliminary Rulings – Another Infant Disease”, (2000) 25 E.L. Rev. 538.

⁵⁴ Opinion of Advocate General F. Jacobs in Case C-136/00 Danner [2002] ECR I-8147, para. 38.

⁵⁵ Communication at p. 8.

⁵⁶ See Vassilios Skouris, “Self-Conception, Challenges and Perspectives of the EU Courts”, in: Pernice, I., Kokott, J. and Saunders, C. (eds): *The Future of the European Judicial System in a Comparative Perspective* (Nomos 2006) at pp. 21-22.

⁵⁷ Communication at p. 8.

preliminary references) has remained insignificant. Thus the celebrated 3.1-month reduction in the length of proceedings in preliminary references⁵⁸ may be easily explained by the fact that there were more judges to decide almost the same number of cases. It is doubtful whether this is a systemic change that will outlast the new Member States courts' shyness about making preliminary references and/or new litigants' lack of experience in using Community courts. Moreover, even 20.4 months of the preliminary ruling procedure is far too much time in some cases where a speedy solution is particularly needed.

The Commission refers to the special procedures, which in its opinion allow closing the case faster than usual. Alas, a closer look at the practice of the Court of Justice and the results of this practice suggest something *very* different. The expedited procedure pursuant to Article 104a of the Rules of Procedure cannot be used as a tool which the Court may use in urgent cases where individual justice or the need for a speedy procedure are at stake – for example criminal procedures where the person concerned awaits the court's judgment in custody, cases of asylum seekers who must often wait for a decision while their personal liberty is restricted or economic operators seeking speedy judgment in order to not be put out of business. Out of 26 cases where the referring court asked for an expedited procedure, the Court satisfied only one request,⁵⁹ which is the result of a particularly restrictive standard.⁶⁰ It is true that the Court could relax the standard, but Article 104a of the Rules of Procedure itself speaks about granting the expedited treatment only in matters of *exceptional* urgency. In other words, expedited treatment cannot be a rule – otherwise the provision would lose its meaning. Thus it cannot be considered as a systemic remedy for the length of proceedings before the Court of Justice.⁶¹

Another suggested solution, the simplified procedure, which in accordance with Article 104(3) of the Rules of Procedure allows the Court of Justice to decide by a reasoned order, does not seem to be a real solution either, although it is considered to be more promising than the expedited procedure.⁶² Again, it is scarcely used. In 2005, 12 reasoned orders were issued, 22 in 2004, 11 in 2003 and 12 in 2002. Perhaps it is a matter of taste. Presidents of the Court of Justice have constantly described the procedure as being “regular” or “frequent.”⁶³ But even if we were ready to accept that 4.72% (i.e. 12 orders out of the total of 254 preliminary references completed in 2005) is a significant percentage, there would be other reasons to believe that the simplified procedure does not help in urgent cases. Statistics of judicial activity do not provide information on the average length of procedure dealt with by reasoned order. So, take a seat and a deep breath; in 2005 it was 18.6 months!⁶⁴ Even if in our

⁵⁸ The Commission refers to the Court's press release No. 14/06 of 13 February 2006, “Statistics concerning judicial activity in 2005 – consolidation and continuation of the progress recorded in 2004”, available at <<http://www.curia.europa.eu/en/actu/communiqués/cp06/info/cp060014en.pdf>>.

⁵⁹ Court of Justice's Annual Report for 2005 at p. 204. Annual reports are available at <<http://www.curia.europa.eu/en/instit/presentationfr/rapport.htm>>.

⁶⁰ See Eric Barbier de la Serre, “Accelerated and Expedited Procedures before the EC Courts: A Review of the Practice”, (2006) 43 C.M.L. Rev. 783 at pp. 796-801.

⁶¹ After all, the Court of Justice admits this in its Discussion Paper at p. 2.

⁶² De la Serre, *op. cit.* n. 60 at p. 811.

⁶³ “The Court made frequent use of the simplified procedure” said President G.C. Rodríguez Iglesias in 2002 (Court of Justice's Annual Report for 2002 at p. 8), while in 2004 President V. Skouris qualified the use as “regular” (Court of Justice's Annual Report for 2004 at p. 13).

⁶⁴ Jan F.K. Inghelram, “Enkele kanttekeningen bij de vereenvoudigde procedure voor de beantwoording van prejudiciële vragen door het HvJ EG”. S.E.W. (Sociaal-economische wetgeving) 2005, p. 452, gives statistics on all years when the procedure was applied, in comparison to the ordinary procedure (number in parenthesis). Thus

calculation we do not take into account the probably extraordinary case *Azienda Agricola Nardoni*,⁶⁵ which took almost 5.5 years to decide, the average length remains at 13.8 months. Would this improve judicial protection available to a person in custody or an asylum seeker?

However, the most compelling reason showing that the simplified procedure is not an instrument speeding up the proceedings in urgent cases lies (as in the case of the expedited procedure) in its very nature. It may be used only in cases where:

[a] question referred to the Court for a preliminary ruling is identical to a question on which the Court has already ruled, where the answer to such a question may be clearly deduced from existing case-law or where the answer to the question admits of no reasonable doubt.⁶⁶

Recall that the Commission’s proposal concerns the Area of Freedom, Security and Justice, one of the most dynamically developing areas of EU law. The questions arising before national courts will hardly be identical, clearly deducible from the Court of Justice’s previous case-law or raising no reasonable doubts, and the simplified procedure will be excluded in most cases.⁶⁷

In sum, due to a relatively small proportion of cases dealt with by reasoned orders and the still considerable length of the procedure, it is not true that the simplified procedure can significantly help the Court of Justice to reduce its backlog of pending cases, which could shorten the average length of proceeding before the Court of Justice. At the same time, the procedure cannot help in individual cases due to its very nature and purpose.

b) Judicial efficiency and the need for a real discourse in the EU judicial process

The Court of Justice may speed up the procedure by another measure. According to Article 20 of the Statute the Court may determine cases without an Opinion of the Advocate General where they do not raise any new point of law. According to the Court’s Annual Report for 2005, about 35 % of judgments in 2005 were delivered without an Opinion (compared with 30 % in 2004).⁶⁸ Again, as in the case of the simplified procedure, the Report does not tell us how much time this saved. However, not only should this interest us here. Much more noticeable is the fact that the Court is willing to cut off an important component of its argumentation⁶⁹ for the sake of the expeditiousness of its work. It is a mark of a broader development, which indicates that the Court of Justice has decided to deal with its caseload by focusing on the *quantity* rather than on the *quality* of its judicial production. This, perhaps unconsciously, significantly undermines its role as a veritable Supreme or even Constitutional Court of the EU.⁷⁰ Critical evaluation of the argumentative practices of the Court of Justice would deserve detailed consideration, which cannot be made here; an often-quoted passage from J. Weiler’s article is submitted instead:

in 2004 it was 18.4 months (23.5), in 2003 20.2 months (25.5), in 2002 17.1 months (24.1), in 2001 16.2 months (22.7), in 2000 30.5 months (21.6), in 1999 8.3 months (21.2) and in 1998 20.2 months (21.4).

⁶⁵ Joined Cases C-483/00, 485/00-488/00, C-492/00-C-494/00, C-496/00 and C-500/00 *Azienda Agricola Nardoni*, not yet reported.

⁶⁶ Article 104(3) of the Rules of Procedure.

⁶⁷ See also n. 38 supra.

⁶⁸ Court of Justice’s Annual Report for 2005 at p. 11.

⁶⁹ See Mitchel de S.O.L. Lasser, *Judicial Deliberations. A Comparative Analysis of Judicial Transparency and Legitimacy* (Oxford University Press, 2004).

⁷⁰ Discussed in part IV. a) infra.

[T]he Court should abandon the cryptic, Cartesian style which still characterizes many of its decisions and move to the more discursive, analytic and conversational style associated more with the common law world – though practiced by others as well, notably the German Constitutional court. As noted above, especially in its Constitutional jurisprudence, it is crucial that the Court display in its judgments that national sensibilities were fully considered and taken into account. And it must amply explain and reason its decisions if they are to be not only authoritarian but also authoritative. The Cartesian style with its pretense of logical legal reasoning and inevitability of results is not conducive to a good conversation with national courts.⁷¹

The Court has remained deaf to this appeal. Moreover, it seems to prefer the exact opposite. This may be illustrated by a recent and quite unfortunate development in the structure of the Court of Justice's judgments. To make them shorter (and thus reduce translation costs), the Court now sometimes leaves out all arguments submitted to the Court by participants – including the Member States. A sublime example is a recent judgment in *Banca popolare di Cremona*.⁷² The case concerned compatibility of an Italian tax with the Community VAT system. Advocate General Jacobs suggested declaring the Italian tax incompatible with EC law and at the same time proposed to the Court that it limits the temporal scope of its judgment. Retroactive effects of the judgment (which is a general rule) would have caused serious economic difficulties for Italy resulting from the duty of Italian authorities to reimburse the amounts collected contrary to EC law.⁷³ The Court re-opened the oral stage of the procedure, asking the parties and the Member States to present further observations concerning interpretation of the relevant provisions of the Sixth Directive and also the possibility of limiting the temporal effects of its decision.⁷⁴ At the second hearing, fourteen Member States submitted their views, and Advocate General Stix-Hackl⁷⁵ - who delivered the second opinion - again proposed declaring the Italian tax incompatible.⁷⁶ However, in its judgment the Court presented the case as a straightforward issue, without mentioning the dissenting opinions of both advocates general, the existence of the second hearing, or the arguments of the Member States.

Quite frustrating for the participating governments (but also for the Court of Justice's observers) must be the judgment in *i-21 Germany*,⁷⁷ where the Court in answering the second question reproduced only the arguments of the applicant in the main proceedings and the Commission, which conveyed its analysis while totally ignoring the arguments presented by governments arguing against its conclusion. One cannot help but ask whether this respects the fundamental principle of equal treatment in judicial procedure.

Elimination of the Member States' arguments from the Court of Justice's judgments does not only mean that the judgment cannot be properly justified; how do we e.g. know that the Court of Justice did not simply overlook some compelling arguments, presented by a Member State

⁷¹ Joseph Weiler, "Epilogue: The Judicial Après Nice" in: de Búrca G., Weiler J.H.H. (eds) *The European Court of Justice* (Oxford University Press, 2001) at p. 225, references omitted.

⁷² Case C-475/03 *Banca popolare di Cremona*, not yet reported.

⁷³ Opinion of Advocate General Jacobs of 17 March 2005 in Case C-475/03 *Banca popolare di Cremona*, not yet reported.

⁷⁴ Order of the Court of 21 October 2005 in Case C-475/03 *Banca popolare di Cremona*, not yet reported.

⁷⁵ Advocate General Stix-Hackl was called to give the second opinion as in the meantime Advocate General Jacobs had resigned from office.

⁷⁶ Opinion of Advocate General Stix-Hackl of 14 March 2006 in Case C-475/03 *Banca popolare di Cremona*, not yet reported.

⁷⁷ Joined Cases C-392/04 and C-422/04 *i-21 Germany*, not yet reported.

or a party to the main proceedings in contradiction to the solution adopted by the Court?⁷⁸ The Court is thus diminishing the importance of the Member States in the European legal discourse, ignoring implications of this for its own legitimacy.⁷⁹ When the President of the Court of Justice discusses potential criticisms of the “quality of the Court of Justice’s case law”, he does not address the quality of the Court’s reasoning at all. He instead “confutes” attacks on the Court for its activism or faintheartedness in cases concerning controversial questions, an issue which relates far more to a substantive evaluation of the Court’s decision-making activity than to something close to the “quality” of its work.⁸⁰

The little care for real discourse in the EU judicial process is also illustrated by the Court of Justice’s proposal for an “urgent preliminary ruling procedure”, discussed further below. Efficiency is seen in cutting off some (perhaps disturbing?) voices, which stand in the way of the Court’s expediency. It is the legitimizing potential of the real discourse, which should urge all concerned to a very careful use of this new procedure, although its adoption seems necessary.⁸¹

It may be argued that the Court of Justice only adjusts its way of reasoning for its audience – which consists predominantly of lower courts that are not interested in long justifications and are only keen to get an answer from the Luxembourg oracle. This may be true, but then the Court of Justice can hardly expect such improperly reasoned answers to seem authoritative before national supreme courts, which probably are much more critical. It again questions the suitability of the Court of Justice’s talking to all courts in Europe. While perhaps all listen, some obey only with hesitation.

IV. A model proposed: hierarchy and differentiation combined

a) *The Court of Justice as part of national judiciaries – Supreme and Constitutional Court*

The starting point of the following section is non-controversial. We must look at the EU judicial system as a whole – not as a mere conglomerate of the central courts in Luxembourg and the national courts in the Member States, each having a different *quality* – the former being “supranational” courts having tasks similar to all international courts, and the latter “wearing Community law hat” only when EU law enters their court-rooms. They *all* form part of the EU judiciary. While this has “become a truism” in relation to national courts⁸² (perhaps to remind them of obligations they have because of EU membership in the EU), the implications of this understanding for the Court of Justice itself seem to go unnoticed.

⁷⁸ Although, until the submissions of the participants to the procedure are not publicly available (as is the case of e.g. the U.S. Supreme Court), we may never properly control the Court as it always depends on how it presents these arguments (and this is the case even of the Reports for the Hearing –these actually present the *answer* proposed by the party, not its supporting *argumentation*).

⁷⁹ There is no space to analyse the concept of the Court of Justice’s legitimacy. For a possible view see Lasser, *op. cit.* n. 69.

⁸⁰ See Skouris, *op. cit.* n. 56 at pp. 24-25. Would we e.g. discuss whether the principle of EC law primacy, stated by the Court of Justice in Case 6/64 *Costa v ENEL* [1964] ECR 585, was of “first-rate quality”? No, but we would perhaps ask whether the Court properly justified the judgment, in which the principle was inserted into EC law.

⁸¹ For the constitutional significance of a true discourse in the EU judicial process see e.g. Miguel Poiars Maduro, “Sovereignty in Europe: The European Court of Justice and the Creation of a European Political Community” in: Volcansek M.L. and Stack J.F. (eds), *Courts Crossing Borders* (Carolina Academic Press 2005) at p. 52.

⁸² Claes, *op. cit.* n. 23 at p. 3.

The Court of Justice is not merely a “supranational” court. This label is often used to avoid difficult questions. The Court of Justice is a civil, criminal and administrative law court, and in these fields it has *become part of national* judicial structures. It is not like an international court acting *outside* national judicial systems, but rather a supreme court, whose task is to guide lower courts in their application of EU law (“supreme” and “lower” are metaphors; this is not to propose that an actual hierarchy, at least as in national legal systems, exists⁸³). Apart from this “ordinary” law jurisdiction, it acts as the EU Constitutional Court – deciding disputes concerning the division of powers, systemic principles of EU law or fundamental rights of those who are bound by it. This mixed nature makes understanding the Court of Justice and its role within the EU judicial system very complicated.

One of the reasons for this confusion is that the Court of Justice may fulfil all these roles using a single means – the preliminary ruling procedure. This procedure was modelled according to procedures dealing with constitutional questions only, important because of their very nature, and not questions concerning the interpretation of ordinary civil, criminal, or administrative legislation. This has far-reaching implications for today’s EU preliminary ruling procedure, as there is no mechanism ensuring that only important questions will arise before the Court of Justice or make the Court of Justice’s workload through the preliminary references more reasonable. Every court may turn to the Court of Justice and the latter must respond regardless of the importance of the question referred.

In most national judicial systems, the highest courts deal with questions of greater importance. The higher the court, the more the system cares for maintaining its coherence, which at the same time means that individual interests give way to these broader considerations. The Court of Justice and the widely opened doors it has towards all national courts (and litigants before them) contradict this, in the name of the judicial protection of individuals. Why are individuals so important to the Court of Justice?

For the most part this is because the Court of Justice builds its legitimacy and authority (as well as the legitimacy and authority of the whole EU legal order) on its direct relationship to all EU citizens.⁸⁴ As Chalmers puts it: “The operationability and authority of the EU legal order, time and again, became equated with the assertion of EC individual rights before a court and the precedence of judicial authority over other administrative actors.”⁸⁵ Equally, individuals have become an important vehicle for EU law enforcement within the Member States.⁸⁶

Unlike the Court of Justice, e.g. the U.S. Supreme Court does not need to fight for its authority in such a way. That is (probably) why the balance of the EU judicial process is so much deflected in favour of individuals, whilst the Supreme Court justices dare to state publicly that their function is “not to correct errors in the lowest courts, but to secure harmony of decision and the appropriate settlement of questions of general importance.”⁸⁷ As C.

⁸³ Although there are tendencies in the Court of Justice to establish similar means of control to those existing in federal judicial systems – see Komárek, *op. cit.* n. 28.

⁸⁴ See e.g. Daniel Halberstam, “The Bride of Messina: Constitutionalism and Democracy in Europe”, (2005) 30 *E.L.Rev.* 775.

⁸⁵ Chalmers, *op. cit.* n. 6 at p. 3.

⁸⁶ See e.g. C.W.A. Timmermans, “Judicial Protection against the Member States: Articles 169 and 177 Revisited”, in: Curtin, D. and Heukels, T. (eds.), *Institutional Dynamics of European Integration. Essays in Honour of Henry G. Schermers. Vol. II.* (Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, 1994).

⁸⁷ Arthur D. Hellman, “The Shrunken Docket of the Rehnquist Court”, (1996) 9 *Sup.Ct.Rev.* 403 quoting at p. 432 U.S. Supreme Court Justices.

Shapiro observes, “[t]he Supreme Court, [...], has cast itself not as a source of justice for individual litigants or the forum to correct aberrations in the application of law, but rather as providing the structure and guidance necessary for the lower courts to correct or avoid errors.”⁸⁸

Another question immediately arises: if the purpose of the preliminary ruling procedure is to ensure coherent interpretation and application of EU law, is it necessary for the Court of Justice to solve every single case when EU law is unclear? As we have already observed above, experience of other highest courts shows that this is not so.⁸⁹ For example the intensity of the U.S. Supreme Court’s control over the application of federal law by lower courts is relatively low, as it believes that it “can best serve the needs of the national law by laying down broad principles, leaving their application and elaboration largely to the federal courts of appeals and the state appellate courts.”⁹⁰ Thus the Supreme Court not only avoids mere “error correction,” it leaves a great scope of independent action in developing federal law to lower courts. An issue which should be seriously examined is the intensity of the Court of Justice control over EU law application on a national level, and the means as to how to achieve it.⁹¹

One of the options would be some kind of a selection mechanism, a “European certiorari.”⁹² Much has been written about case-selection by the Court of Justice but, in the event, proposals to this effect have never been adopted. This article will not be a further attempt to change the mind of those who have previously rejected case selection. Nevertheless, contrary to the “certiorari option,” limitation of preliminary references to the courts of last instance have always been dismissed too quickly, using the same or similar arguments.⁹³ In addition, this limitation may bring about other beneficial outcomes, resulting from the institutional structures of the national judiciaries, which the Court of Justice’s open doors threaten. Let us consider these advantages.

b) Hierarchy as a means of bringing rationality to the judicial process

Problems that judicial systems must face today do not concern only the supreme courts. They reach far wider and concern all courts in the system, not only its apex. This is caused by the increasingly important role of law and its institutions in the life of society, which has brought about a “litigation explosion,” resulting in an unmanageable caseload for courts. Paradoxically, this simultaneously undermined trust in the courts’ work because the quality of their work diminished due to their workload.⁹⁴ Inevitably, the objective of providing “ideal” justice must be balanced against other interests and constraints limiting the effectiveness of the judicial system. The following will show that establishing the hierarchy of courts is a means of finding a proper balance between various interests and an effective distribution of resources in the judicial system. In fact, the hierarchy of courts is one of the prerequisites for

⁸⁸ Carolyn Shapiro: “The Limits of the Olympian Court: Common Law Judging Versus Error Correction in the Supreme Court”, (2006) 63 Wash. & Lee L. Rev. 271 at p. 279.

⁸⁹ See the text accompanying n. 6-10.

⁹⁰ Hellman, op. cit. 87 at p. 433.

⁹¹ For inspiring discussions concerning the U.S. Supreme Court’s control over application of federal law by lower courts see Hellman, op. cit. 87 or Shapiro, op. cit. n. 88. See also discussion accompanying n. 5-10 supra.

⁹² For a general evaluation see Liz Heffernan, “The Community Courts Post-Nice: A European *Certiorari* Revisited”, (2003) 52 I.C.L.Q. 907.

⁹³ For one of the (most probably few) exceptions see Rasmussen, op. cit. n. 52.

⁹⁴ See Héctor Fix-Fierro, *Courts, Justice and Efficiency: A Socio-legal Study of Economic Rationality in Adjudication* (Hart Publishing, 2004) at pp. 1-33.

a functioning judicial system. The preliminary ruling procedure, in its current design, destabilizes that balance. This has detrimental effects, not only for the national judicial systems but for the EU judiciary as a whole. The Court of Justice's capacity is treated not as a scarce resource, but as an ordinary part of the judicial process. In the Commission's words (which reflect the view of the Court of Justice): "[a]n essential element of the procedure is the principle that *all* national courts can dialogue with the Court."⁹⁵ The consequences will be seen below.

Judicial hierarchy guarantees a rational distribution of resources in several ways. Time and other resources of an economic nature are factors determining whether the judicial system is able to produce just results and whether it is sufficiently inclusive. Another, inherent limitation of the judiciary stems from the unequal competence of individual judges. Being a judge requires experience, education and skills not possessed by all judges to the same extent. "Judicial wisdom" is distributed throughout the system unevenly – more experienced judges generally sit at higher courts, as these courts must solve more difficult questions.⁹⁶ We do not necessarily have to explain the smaller number of references from national supreme (or higher) courts by their unwillingness to submit themselves to the Court of Justice authority. An equally sound explanation may actually be that they are more competent to deal with complex legal questions.⁹⁷

The varied distribution of "judicial wisdom" does not only concern competence of a purely "legal" nature possessed by an experienced judge. The judicial process involves different tasks and requires different skills which are allocated to different levels of the judicial decision-making process. Fact-finding requires, among other things, an ability to examine witnesses or assess their reliability and is usually done at a first instance (trial) level. On the contrary, higher courts do not generally determine facts –rather do they develop law in difficult, "unsettled" cases.⁹⁸ This is particularly true of supreme courts. Their activity must be based not only on a considerable legal expertise, but also on their ability to see the wider societal consequences of their decisions, since in such situations they make law. Again, allowing references from the lower courts means that judges, who do not possess competence or experience to take decisions in a complex institutional and societal context, are involved in difficult cases involving hard choices surpassing the domain of ordinary law in which they are used to operate. A case in point is the Irish abortion litigation, which produced one of the most difficult cases for the Court of Justice, as it had to face a conflict between the constitutional prohibition of abortion and the principles of free movement. Although it may be frustrating for those who want the Court of Justice (or courts) to give definite answers in cases, even if they can reach beyond their institutional competence and scope of law in general, the Court of Justice at the end avoided judging the conflict and so did the Irish Supreme Court. The troubling reference came from a lower court.⁹⁹

⁹⁵ Communication at p. 4. The 1999 Report is on the same wave-length as the Commission. See particularly pp. 22-23.

⁹⁶ See Damaška's examination of varied approaches to distribution of authority within his models of the judiciary (hierarchical and coordinate) depending on qualities valued by a particular system: *The Faces of Justice and State Authority. A Comparative Approach to the Legal Process* (Yale University Press, 1986) at pp. 16-28.

⁹⁷ See Chalmers, op. cit. n. 6 at p. 34 who also rejects a priori distrustful stance towards higher courts.

⁹⁸ Lasser convincingly shows that this is the case also in France, known for its historically determined distrust in the judiciary (see Lasser, op. cit. n. 69). The question is not whether courts make law, but how openly they do so.

⁹⁹ See Claes, op. cit. n. 23 at pp. 526-531. For a general argument showing limitations of courts when deciding constitutional conflicts between supranational and national law see Jan Komárek, "European Constitutionalism

The separation of fact finding from law making on a higher level of the judicial process has more than this rationale. As Damaška puts it:

Initial decisionmakers are closer to the messy details of life, including human drama, and therefore can less readily be immunized from individual aspects of cases. Meanwhile, higher officials face realities prepackaged or edited by their subordinates; individual destinies are less visible. Because of this mediation, higher-ups can more easily disregard the “equities” of the cases they must decide. The advantage of their insensitivity to individual circumstances is that they are free to concern themselves with correcting inconsistencies in low-level decisions and with cultivation of broad ordering schemes for decision-making.¹⁰⁰

This advantage is lost when the first instance court makes a reference to the Court of Justice before the problem has been properly elaborated in the national judicial process. No wonder that the Court of Justice inclines to do justice in particular cases instead of searching for proper interpretation of law, which could be applied in a more general context. “Early” references have another adverse consequence: they may actually eliminate the higher court’s desire to clarify EU law in collaboration with the Court of Justice, as the higher court does not want to prolong the procedure for another two years; although it may consider that it would be desirable to ask different questions to those that had been asked by the lower court.¹⁰¹

More instances at a national level also mean more accuracy in identification of what is necessary to be decided by the Court of Justice. This is explained by the Condorcet theorem which, put briefly, presupposes that “more heads know more”:

[U]nder certain conditions, [...] the cumulative vote of a group of independent decisionmakers, each of whom is more likely than not to get a decision right, will approach greater and greater accuracy as the number in the group increases. More heads are better than fewer, so long as each head is probably right. A related point is that consensus reduces the variance of opinions and thus dampens the effect of extreme views. The typical structure of hierarchical judicial systems illustrates these institutional principles: The number of judges hearing a given case usually increases as the case ascends through the judicial hierarchy, which emphasizes that the most controversial decisions will tend to be made by a larger group of judges.¹⁰²

The need for increasing the quality of the questions referred to the Court of Justice and possible involvement of higher court judges in their formulation is sometimes mirrored in rather odd proposals: Chalmers e.g. suggests that a possible way to select meaningful references “would be for a judge from the Court of Justice and a senior judge from the national jurisdiction to consider together whether a reference made by a national court is appropriate for a ruling by the Court of Justice.”¹⁰³ Instead of creating some kind of “selection committee” composed of the Court of Justice and national supreme courts judges, alien to the

and the European Arrest Warrant – In Search of the Limits of ‘Contrapunctual Principles’”, (2007) 44 C.M.L.Rev. 9 at pp. 34-39.

¹⁰⁰ Damaška, op. cit. n. 96 at p. 20.

¹⁰¹ Such a shortcoming may be eliminated by the possibility of challenging decisions to refer before the higher courts. This seems to be allowed by the Court of Justice (Case 146/73 Rheinmühlen-Düsseldorf [1974] ECR 139, para. 3), and is now being reconsidered in Case C-210/06 Cartesio, OJ C 165, of 15.07.2006, p. 17.

¹⁰² Adrian Vermuele, “Interpretive Choice”, (2000) 75 N.Y.U.L.Rev. 74 at p. 117, footnotes omitted. As to the last point, see the text accompanying n. 99 supra.

¹⁰³ Chalmers, op. cit. n. 6 at pp. 33-34.

judicial process, a national judicial hierarchy through which higher courts would control the activity of lower instances by ordinary procedural means may do the same job.

Thus the division of labour between lower and higher courts enables the latter to fulfil their task, which of course sometimes requires leaving a minor injustice without remedy. In other words, hierarchy ensures (more or less) a rational distribution of cases in the system.¹⁰⁴ The lowest courts decide all issues, and by way of appeals their superior courts check how they succeeded in particularly complicated cases and correct their failures. However, the superior courts' control is not endless and overwhelming. There is only a limited number of instances wherein one may pursue his case, and the higher one climbs in the hierarchy, the less the system cares for his particular case and rather turns its attention to the wider consequences of the judgment for the legal system as a whole. This is achieved by filtering mechanisms, which does not necessarily entail case selection but encounters a much wider means of control.¹⁰⁵ All these advantages are lost if the lowest court in the hierarchy is allowed to turn immediately to the "supreme"¹⁰⁶ interpretative authority. This produces disturbances at national level, which the Court of Justice often ignores, and also burdens the proper functioning of the Union judiciary.

c) The proposal – hierarchy and differentiation

From the foregoing we can formulate a proposal for the preliminary reference procedure regime:

- 1 Limiting preliminary ruling procedure to courts of last instance as a rule;
- 2 As a *necessary* exception to 1, when a lower court considers that one or more arguments for invalidity, put forward by the parties or as the case may be raised by it of its own motion, are well founded, it must stay proceedings and make a reference to the Court for a preliminary ruling on the act's validity;¹⁰⁷
- 3 As a *possible* exception to 1, the Council can decide which EU law measures may be subject to preliminary references from lower courts.

There is not much to be added to points 1 and 2 of the proposal since arguments supporting them have been discussed at some length. As regards point 3, it has already been mentioned that in some instances it may serve the economy of the judicial process to allow references from first instance courts. A case in point was the Brussels regulation,¹⁰⁸ but there would certainly be other measures too.

In addition, some form of an urgent preliminary ruling procedure may be created, as the Court of Justice suggested in its Discussion Paper.¹⁰⁹ The Court was less optimistic than the Commission about the sufficient efficiency of its existing procedures. It proposed creating an

¹⁰⁴ For an analysis using political science modelling, see Lewis A. Kornhauser: "Adjudication by a Resource-Constrained Team: Hierarchy and Precedent in a Judicial System", (1994-1995) 68 S.Cal.L.Rev. 1605.

¹⁰⁵ See *The Role and Future of the European Court of Justice*, (The British Institute of International and Comparative Law, 1996) at pp. 114-115, which gives examples of such selection mechanisms.

¹⁰⁶ See n. 83 for an explanation of the term "supreme" here.

¹⁰⁷ Case C-344/04 International Air Transport Association, not yet reported, para. 30; see the text accompanying n. 47.

¹⁰⁸ See the text accompanying n. 50 supra.

¹⁰⁹ See n. 1.

“urgent preliminary ruling procedure”, since in some instances the ordinary procedure takes too long and limitation of the Court of Justice’s caseload cannot help with it. The Court of Justice’s Discussion Paper¹¹⁰ mentions the regulation concerning jurisdiction and the recognition and enforcement of judgments in matrimonial and parental responsibility matters;¹¹¹ this lays down a number of time-limits applying to the national courts, including a time-limit of six weeks for giving a ruling (except where exceptional circumstances make this impossible) where proceedings are brought before a court seeking the return of a child who has been wrongfully removed. References in criminal cases involving persons in custody represent another example.

The Court of Justice’s proposal cannot be examined in detail here; however, brief perusal of it shows that its simplification consists primarily in the limitation of a true discourse and exchange of opinions between the parties, Member States and EU institutions. This would be acceptable in cases of minor importance; but, such cases should never arise before the Court of Justice, if it ever wants to become a veritable supreme and constitutional court for the whole Union. Such cases should be dealt with primarily by national courts and only if important reach the ultimate authority of the Court of Justice.

This does not mean, that in matters of urgency, the protection of individuals would somehow suffer because of their need to climb the national judicial pyramid. National procedural law may provide itself for an expedited procedure, whereby such cases would reach the national supreme court more speedily. Moreover, expediency of the national procedures is often underestimated. In a recent case *Bot*,¹¹² a reference from the French *Conseil d’Etat*, it took only six weeks since a decree of deportation had been issued against the appellant in the main proceedings until the *Conseil d’Etat*’s referred to the Court of Justice, when a lower court had rejected an application for the decree’s annulment. The urgent procedure should therefore be possible only after a last instance court’s reference and not in every case concerning individual rights. It could easily become a standard procedure, and the legitimacy of the EU judicial process would be further undermined.

V. Conclusion

Narrowing down the possibility of lower courts to send preliminary references reflects the philosophy of the Court of Justice’s role as a veritable Supreme Court for the Union and its courts. Supreme, not because of its hierarchically superior position over the national courts – this article does not advocate such a position. The article believes that the fundamental Court of Justice’s task, when ensuring that in the interpretation and application of the Treaties the law is observed,¹¹³ is to provide national courts with authoritative guidance. However, to be able to speak with authority, the Court must speak clearly and persuasively. This cannot be done if it pulverizes its authority into hundreds of (sometimes) contradictory and (often) insufficiently reasoned answers. The current system of preliminary reference, which undermines national judicial structures by allowing the lowest parts of the judicial pyramid to

¹¹⁰ Discussion Paper at p. 2.

¹¹¹ Council Regulation (EC) No 2201/2003 of 27 November 2003 concerning jurisdiction and the recognition and enforcement of judgments in matrimonial matters and the matters of parental responsibility, repealing Regulation (EC) No 1347/2000, OJ 2003 L 338, p. 1.

¹¹² Case 241/05 *Bot*, not yet reported.

¹¹³ Article 220 EC.

talk directly to the ultimate interpretative authority, has negative effects both for the national judicial process and for the Court of Justice's mission.

This article has considered an option which thus has received scant attention – limiting the power of lower courts to refer while at the same time adopting differentiated procedures in accordance with the nature of the instrument to be interpreted. The article showed that many arguments against such an approach are not sufficiently thought out and are used rather mechanically. Even if the proposal contained here does not persuade the reader, perhaps – and still importantly – the article will facilitate an open-minded discussion of the current structure of the EU judicial system.